

IDLE, Inclusive Digital Laboratory for Experimental Art, utilizes Hydra as a virtual instrument within a 3D environment, transitioning from live coding performances to collaborative installations.

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ABSTRACT

IDLE, Inclusive Digital Laboratory for Experimental Art, is an innovative and inclusive art project based in Bergen, utilizing Studio 207 as a digitally updated art venue. Through the Virtual Gallery, artists and audiences can remotely control the venue's audiovisual devices via the Internet.

To further expand the interactive offerings of the Virtual Gallery, the artists Flor de Fuego and Blaž Pavlica were invited to develop an interactive visual instrument in the IDLE platform (WebVR) based on live coding using HYDRA within a VR environment. The residency started in September and concluded in November 2023, timed to align with the Piksel Festival.

1. INTRODUCTION

IDLE, Inclusive Digital Laboratory for Experimental Art, is an innovative and inclusive art project based in Bergen, utilizing Studio 207 as a digitally updated art venue. Through the Virtual Gallery, artists and audiences can remotely control the venue's audiovisual devices via the Internet.

To further expand the interactive offerings of the Virtual Gallery, the artists Flor de Fuego and Blaž Pavlica were invited to a three month long IDLE residency to develop a new creative software based on live coding using HYDRA within a VR environment. The residency started in September and concluded in November 2023, timed to align with the Piksel Festival.

The primary objective of this residency, workshop and performance was to delve into the potential of Web VR as a powerful tool for engaging everyone in interactive encounters. Producing a creative instrument with free/libre technologies worked as a mean of sustainability and openness to the artistic community, enabling people with less experience to work on these new visuals languages, which also helped to expand their creative minds.

By facilitating new artistic experiences and fostering creative collaboration, all without requiring physical presence, the residency resulted in:

- An interactive visual instrument in the IDLE platform (WebVR)
- A performance showcasing the artistic potential of using hydra in a Virtual Gallery
- A presentation of the process and results

- A workshop on Hydra aimed at Kids and Youngsters.
- Enhanced knowledge regarding the possibilities presented by Web VR and Hydra.

2. DEVELOPMENT

2.1 Overview

The residency generated a new visual interactive instrument based on Hydra Live Coding, which was manipulated at the virtual gallery, modifying the visuals and lights in both venues, the virtual and the physical one. This was a unique project that expanded the expertise of the artists and challenged them to "open and connect" their knowledge to new technological systems.

The project joined cutting-edge technological tools applied to art and creativity while enabling a professional creative and developer environment. IDLE was noticed in the international electronic art arena, which also brought the artists an international projection.

IDLE is an ongoing multi-disciplinary three-year project from 2022-2024. Along 2022/23, Píksel developed the main infrastructure systems to "communicate" the virtual gallery to the physical venue. The core of this residency was to expose the artists to the new technological systems to work on defining an innovative visual instrument based on Hydra, accessible via the virtual gallery to affect the art venue in Bergen.

The artists were exposed to IoT (Internet Of Things) devices, Sound and Video control interfaces, and Virtual Reality user interfaces; The electronically updated infrastructure spoiled new challenges for them.

IDLE at this stage unified different art practices. The artists worked on live coding HYDRA. The goal was to join their expertise to develop an instrument that could act as an installation where people could play collaboratively to change the visuals in both the virtual gallery and the physical art venue. In doing so, the artists were for the first time confronted with new applications of their own expertise, expanding the way they saw the tools they used in their artistic practice.

IDLE is a project initiated by Píksel in 2022, in collaboration with CNDS, Malitzin Cortés and Iván Abreu, APO33, Jenny Pickett, Julien Ottavi, Romain Papion, Maite Cajaraville, Gisle Frøysland, Alexander Crawford and Martin E. Koch.

Residents Blaz and Flor, joined a professional creative and developer environment to improve their knowledge. To work on one of the most innovative projects in Europe that joined alter-verse worlds, live coding, instruments, and for the first time united physical and virtual art experiences. They produced a creative tool with free/libre technologies as a means of sustainability and openness to the artistic community, enabling people with less experience to work on these new visual languages, which also helped to spread their creative minds.

IDLE got attention in the international arenas, for its inclusiveness and the actual need for people with other capacities to get together virtually, augmenting their access to socialize while enjoying culture. Bringing them new possibilities to interact, play together, and enjoy new art experiences created by them.

IDLE was an ongoing project that had been presented at different development stages at ISEA (International Symposium for Electronic Arts in Paris, in June 2023, Píksel 2022, Festspill in Bergen, and featured on the Spanish National Television program "Metrópolis". This new development would also be presented at different festivals and to international cultural organizations.

2.2 The HYDRA Virtual Instrument on IDLE

The IDLE residency aimed to create a new visual interactive instrument using Hydra Live Coding. This instrument was to be manipulated at the virtual gallery, allowing modifications to the visuals and lights in both the virtual and physical venues.

Using hydra instances in the Virtual Realm a virtual instrument was created in the shape of frog-shaped avatars with whom the audience can interact. The avatar frogs are on their end acting and interacting with the IoT lights that are installed in the physical space. By interacting and manipulating the avatar frogs placed in the virtual gallery, visitors are permitted modifications to the visuals and lights, both in the virtual and physical venues.

In order to control the hydra instances inside the Cyber Gallery, a new interface was created and implemented. To further enhance the audience experience, a new physical-virtual window was created, permitting participants to enjoy the other side of the interface.

Figure 1, 2. Audience interacting with IDLE. Photo © Píksel, 2023.

Figure 3. Users interacting with IDLE. Photo © Píksel, 2023.

Figure 4. Users interacting with IDLE. Photo © Pikel, 2023.

Figure 5. Virtual visual instrument interface through frogs. Photo © Pikel, 2023.

This was a unique project that expanded the expertise of the artists and participants, challenging them to “open and connect” their knowledge to new technological systems. As seasoned Hydra users and performers, the artists in residency got to explore new and innovative ways of utilizing Hydra by implementing it to the developed Virtual Gallery.

2.3 The results. Presentation, Performance and Workshops.

To finalize the residency and share the results, the artist's three months with the IDLE team concluded with a week-long stay in Bergen. Here the artists got to test the instrument in the physical venue.

At the end of the week, Flor and Blaz presented the final results to an eager audience attending the Píksel Festival Opening. Sharing the steps taking, the process and inquiries made, the attendees at studio 207 got a unique insight to the unlocked potential of Web VR.

Figure 6 and 7. Blaz and Flor explaining to the audience the virtual instrument working on IDLE . Photo © Andreas A. Thomsen, 2023.

As the evening progressed, visitors were able to interact with the web camera connected to a screen featuring visual effects coded in to manipulate the real time images using the Hydra features.

For the closing of the festival, the artists again emerged in the spotlight with a visual performance, utilizing the instruments created to showcase the artistic use.

Figure 8. IDLE and Hydra performance at Studio 207, Bergen Píksel Festival 2023 . Photo © Píksel, 2023.

Figure 9. IDLE and Hydra performance at Studio 207, Bergen Píksel Festival 2023 . Photo © Píksel, 2023.

Figure 10. Audience attending IDLE and Hydra performance at Studio 207, Bergen Píksel Festival 2023. Photo © Píksel, 2023.

Through the workshops “Live coding with Hydra” participants got introduced to creation and modification of code and algorithms resulting in visual effects produced in real-time.

The workshops introduced participants to the Hydra live coding platform, a live codeable video synth and coding environment that runs directly in the browser. It is free and open-source, made for beginners and experts alike.

Throughout the 3 hours of workshop repeating for three consecutive days, kids and youngsters got introduced to the art of coding as a visual performative method, with examples to pique interest.

Figure 11. Images from different workshops on Hydra and IDLE at Studio 207 . Photo © Píksel, 2023.

3. CONCLUSIONS

Hydra is emerging as a highly potent tool for integration within three.js environments. There are various avenues to explore for extending Hydra's advancements into the IDLE three-dimensional environment:

1. Facilitating direct connection of Hydra sketch variables through avatars' interactions in the virtual world, allowing for a more seamless integration. Currently, we are limited to merely "selecting" different Hydra sketches.
2. Establishing a linkage between Hydra performances and the IoT lights within the physical gallery, creating a cohesive interaction between the virtual and physical elements of the environment.

Acknowledgments

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